

Quick guide to the grass long bodied orb-web spiders (Araneae: Araneidae) in South Africa

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Plant-living spiders have a range of characteristic adaptations that facilitate a life on and under bark, in grass, on flowers, among foliage or on sea. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), all available information on spider species distribution in the South African Grassland Biome was compiled until the end of 2011 and 58 families, 275 genera and 792 described species have been recorded (Haddad *et al.*, 2013).

Grass dwellers are easily recognised by their elongated bodies and long, thin legs. They vary in colour from green to fawn and many are cryptically coloured with stripes along their length, imitating the veins in a blade of grass. They are especially difficult to detect while at rest, when the legs are held forward and parallel with the body. Grass dwellers typically tie twisted grass blades and grass seeds together with their silk threads to create a retreat or to deposit their egg sac (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023).

Kilima decens (Blackwall, 1866)

Epigyne after Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia bifida Tullgren, 1910

After Grasshoff (1970)

Larinia chloris (Audouin, 1826)

After Grasshoff (1970)

***Larinia longissima* (Simon, 1881) (preciously *Lipocrea*)**

***Larinia natalensis* (Grasshoff, 1971)**

***Mahemba hewitti* (Lessert, 1930)**

***Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863)**

***Paralarinia bartelsi* (Lessert, 1933)**

Peter Webb

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After Grasshoff (1970)

FURTHER READING

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